

BRIEFING PAPER

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The epidemiology, aetiology, treatment, and experiences of PANS/PANDAS: an evidence and gap map

Paediatric Acute-Onset Neuropsychiatric Syndrome (PANS) and Paediatric Autoimmune Neuropsychiatric Disorders Associated with Streptococcal infections (PANDAS) are related conditions characterised by the abrupt onset of severe neuropsychiatric symptoms like obsessive-compulsive behaviours, tics, or severe restrictive eating.^{1,2} Complex issues surround these conditions: 1) poor awareness, 2) a lack of global agreement of symptomatology, 3) a lack of definitive biomarkers, and 4) no clear consensus on how to treat and manage PANS or PANDAS. For those living with the conditions and their families, navigating these conditions can be life-changing, traumatic and isolating.

To capture evidence about these conditions, identify gaps, and help plan future research, we created an evidence and gap map (EGM) to collate all available empirical evidence on PANS/PANDAS across the following research topics: diagnosis, epidemiology, aetiology/pathology, symptoms, treatment, treatment aims, access to services, and experiences.

This is a high-level overview of our research to inform decision-making. Further outputs including plain language summaries and full reports are available:

Snapshot of PANS and PANDAS

The term PANDAS was proposed in 1998 by Swedo et al. to describe a subset of OCD cases with the following criteria: 1) presence of OCD or tic disorder, 2) prepubertal onset, 3) acute symptom onset with fluctuating course, 4) association with neurological signs, and 5) temporal association with a streptococcal infection.¹

PANS was defined in 2012 to encompass related disorders not associated with streptococcal infections.²

PANS/PANDAS is recognised as a research priority in the James Lind Alliance's top 10 priorities for childhood neurological disorders.³

What is an evidence and gap map (EGM)?

An EGM is an interactive visual representation of the distribution of evidence across a topic according to predefined characteristics. It also highlights where gaps in a research base may exist. You can access our EGM here: [PANS/PANDAS EGM](#)

Key Findings

- Over half of the available evidence on PANS/PANDAS comes from the USA, with UK-based studies representing only about 5% of the evidence.
- Much of the evidence was composed of studies with low scientific rigour; many of these case studies, and only 5 randomised control trials (RCT) have been conducted on PANS or PANDAS treatment to date.
- Very few systematic reviews have been published.
- The rate at which PANS/PANDAS evidence is produced has increased dramatically in the last 10 years.
- Although gaps in the evidence base exist across all areas of research, there is enough to produce evidence syntheses across all these areas.

Why and how did we do this review?

Review rationale – the ‘why’

There is a lack of consensus about the aetiology, diagnosis, and treatment of PANS/PANDAS. This uncertainty is brought on and compounded by a fractured, poorly collated evidence base, leaving clinicians with little to no guidance on how to diagnose, treat, and manage these conditions. This puts the onus on patients and their families to manage severe symptoms and cope with misdiagnoses and limited options for treatment.

We created this EGM to give clinicians, patients, and their families access to all available research on PANS/PANDAS. Identifying the gaps in the evidence base may help to guide directions for future research.

We were commissioned by the NIHR Evidence Synthesis Programme to conduct this research.

This EGM is Stage 1 of our evidence synthesis project into these conditions: PANS PANDAS Unveiled.

Image hand-drawn by A. Stitt using Sketchbook Pro

Patient and Public Involvement and Engagement

Two PPIE groups (made up of children and young people, and parents/guardians) and interest holders (clinicians and PANS PANDAS UK representative) were involved in the creation of this EGM from inception to completion. The PPIE groups were recruited from the PANS PANDAS UK website, social media, and Youth Board members, as well as via the NIHR PenARC's local and national networks. We met with these groups online throughout the project, integrating their feedback on the protocol, the EGM, the report, and the plain language summary. They shared with us their lived experience of these conditions; their knowledge and expertise shaped the structure and features of this EGM and served as guidance for how to make the EGM as widely accessible as possible. As a team, we are incredibly grateful for the insight into the experiences of PANS/PANDAS that these young people and their families brought to this project.

Image hand-drawn by A. Stitt using Sketchbook Pro

Overview of the evidence

We included journal articles, conference abstracts, abstracts, and theses if they contained empirical evidence on PANS, PANDAS, or both. Database searching yielded 5,260 records, with 2,087 of these removed as duplicate records. The remaining 3,172 records were screened at title and abstract; 2,506 of these were excluded, leaving 667 records for retrieval. Of these 18 were not found and 649 were assessed for eligibility through screening of the full-text of each record; 411 of these records met inclusion criteria. A further 34 records were included from supplementary searching, with 445 records ultimately included in this EGM.

What did we find?

Overview of Findings

- We created this EGM by classifying (coding) the relevant qualities and content of each included study.
- Our EGM is organised along two axes: Research topic (x) and Year of publication (y).
- Each included study was also coded by study design: case report/series, retrospective/observational/cross sectional, prospective cohort, systematic review, randomised controlled trial, and qualitative.
- The EGM utilises a filter system, allowing users to select their own parameters when navigating the contents of the EGM.

A snapshot of our EGM findings:

Distribution of evidence by research topic

- **Symptoms** was the most coded research topic, followed by **aetiology/pathophysiology** and **treatment effectiveness**.
- **Study design** skewed towards **case reports/series** and **retrospective/observational/cross sectional**.
- Studies in the **Diagnosis** topic were often coded with involvement of diverse healthcare professionals.
- Studies in the **epidemiology** topic mostly focused on flares/relapses rather than prevalence.
- Within the **aetiology/pathophysiology** topic, there were nearly twice as many studies on PANDAS compared to PANS.

- The top codes in the **symptoms** topic were: **obsessive-compulsive behaviour; tics; anxiety; irritability, anger, and aggression**.
- **Antibiotics, Intravenous immunoglobulins (IVIg) and Therapeutic Plasma Exchange (TPE)/ plasmapheresis, and psychiatric medication** were the most coded **treatments**; however, studies within the **treatment** topic were dominated primarily by case reports/studies.
- Most studies in the **experiences** topic reported on parent and child (patient) experiences; no qualitative evidence synthesis of experiences have yet been conducted.

Distribution of coding across study regions

*Central America included in North America
Created with Datawrapper

What are the implications of this review?

By mapping all the current empirical data on PANS/PANDAS, this EGM can serve as a reference point for the current state of the evidence we have on these conditions and is accessible to not only clinicians, but patients and their caregivers. This EGM can benefit organisations such as the PANS Clinical Guideline Development Group, which seeks to produce clinical guidelines based on existing knowledge and expert consensus.

Read our report here:

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We are one of 13 research groups in the UK commissioned by the National Institute for Health and Care Research [Evidence Synthesis Programme](#) to address knowledge gaps or to answer a specific need for health, public health and social care audiences.

Limitations and strengths

This EGM was informed by clinicians, patients, and their families who have extensive lived experience with PANS/PANDAS, increasing its relevance to those most directly affected by these conditions.

Although this EGM was commissioned with a UK focus in mind, less than 5% of the evidence came from the UK

However, the identification of this gap in the research base may provide incentive for more UK-based research into PANS/PANDAS.

We only included evidence about PANS or PANDAS (or related terms). Studies including patients with a similar presentation of symptoms but not confirmed to be PANS or PANDAS by study authors were excluded.

However, the inclusion of similar cases would have been confusing for those accessing and navigating the map for information on PANS/PANDAS.

Some codes were difficult to record in the map due to a lack of clarity or a lack of reporting within the included studies.

Our broad inclusion criteria ensured that we captured any and all empirical evidence on PANS/PANDAS and were not limited by publication status.

However, it's possible that because our criteria was so broad, we may have included evidence that is not very useful.

Future research

- Through this EGM we have identified gaps within every research topic of PANS/PANDAS. Further research into the aetiology and pathophysiology of these conditions is urgently needed, as there is a need to address the underlying mechanisms of PANS/PANDAS to effectively treat and manage symptoms.
- Based on the recent acceleration of PANS/PANDAS research in the last 10 years, further evidence synthesis across various research topics is needed –especially in the areas of treatment effectiveness and experiences of these conditions.
- There is a need for more rigorous, prospective studies to evaluate the effectiveness of treatments for PANS/PANDAS such as antibiotics, behavioural interventions, and psychiatric medication.

References

1. Swedo SE, Leonard HL, Garvey M, Mittleman B, Allen AJ, Perlmutter S, et al. Pediatric autoimmune neuropsychiatric disorders associated with streptococcal infections: Clinical description of the first 50 cases. *American Journal of Psychiatry*. 1998;155(2):264-71.
2. Swedo SE, Leckman JF, Rose NR. From research subgroup to clinical syndrome: modifying the PANDAS criteria to describe PANS (pediatric acute-onset neuropsychiatric syndrome). *Pediatr Therapeut*. 2012;2(2):113.
3. James Lind Alliance. Childhood Neurological Conditions 2024 [Available from: <https://www.jla.nihr.ac.uk/priority-setting-partnerships/childhood-neurological-conditions#tab-top-10-priorities>].